

ADSORPTION, KINETICS AND THERMODYNAMICS STUDIES ON REMEDIATION OF DYES USING HALLOYSITE NANOTUBES AND UNMODIFIED CLAY MINERALS

SYNOPSIS

1. Introduction

The ever-increasing population and living standard have created an increasing demand for textiles and clothing - one of the primary needs of human beings. Dyes have a long history of invention and development constitutes an important component of our daily lives. The magnitude and growth of dye industry is intricately linked to that of the Indian textile industry which produced an astonishing 46.1 million Kgs of fabric in 2014 and used billions of liters of water leading to the unprecedented demand to address the issues of carbon and water foot prints of textile industry. Bringing down water footprint and carbon footprint is the ultimate concern for sustainable development of world's textile industry. Amongst the existing many industries, textile industries are considered as one amongst the top ten most polluting industries. Predictions about the rapid growth of the textile industry in coming decades due to several factors including growing population, increasing disposable income, and changing consumer trends will present new challenges to the scientists, technologist and policy makers to find new avenues.

Textile industries use varieties of chemicals and are one of the major consumers of dyes. Reactive dyes are the most prominent classes of chemicals which are used extensively in textile industries. Most of the reactive dyes come under the category of azo dyes. Azo dyes have a high degree of chemical and photolytic stability and this property is of great concern for pollution abatement. Azo dyes toxicity is generally not because of the dye itself, but due to its biotransformation and/or degradation product(s) which display high level of acute and chronic toxicity and carcinogenicity

A large number of techniques, methods and procedures are used for the disposal of effluents. They can be broadly classified as physical, chemical, and biological techniques and these are applied to treat effluents containing dyes and heavy metals. However, they have limitations and disadvantages for one reason or the other. Adsorption techniques, of late are gaining prominence due to their efficiency in the removal of pollutants that are otherwise too stable for conventional methods.

1.2 Overview

About the thesisin brief

To address the daunting task of textile industrial effluents which releases about 28,000 tons of dyes every year into the environment – a simple low-cost and low energy technique, namely, adsorption is used using the adsorbents which are abundantly available in large quantities. Two classes of adsorbents, namely, inorganic materials and agro-based biomass are used as eco-friendly and low materials for the remediation of toxic dyes from the industrial effluents. To understand the behavior of the adsorbents and exploring the possibilities of extending to use clean technology; the following minerals are selected for my study: bentonite, kaolin light, montmorillonite K10 and halloysite nanotube. I have selected three dyes which are used extensively in the textile industries in India. They are; Direct Blue 15, Direct Red 13 and Brilliant Green. The former two dyes belong to bis azo dye class of compounds and the latter, namely, brilliant green belongs to the triarylmethane dyes class of compounds. The outline of the thesis is presented here for clarity and ready reference. Each unit of the thesis is presented as an independent unit and culminates with the relevant references.

1.3 Structure of chapters

About the chapters.....in brief

PART A

Chapter 1 presents an overview of the environmental pollution caused by major industries with a reference to textile industries and nutraceutical industries. Remediation strategy of dyes from textile industrial effluent has been presented using halloysite nanotubes and abundantly available unmodified clay minerals which are eco-friendly and cost-effective.

PART B

This part consists of two chapters and devoted to the remediation studies using halloysite nanotubes.

Chapter 2 describes a novel laboratory scale experiments are designed to allude to the concept of Circular Economy (CE) through remediation of Direct Blue 15 (DB15) dye using abundantly available and nontoxic halloysite nanotubes (HNT) and their application to textile industrial effluent (TIE). The DB15 adsorbed-HNT “sludge” was used as reinforcing material along with plastic waste for the fabrication of composites. To understand the phenomena of DB15 adsorption on HNT as a prelude to commercialization; various factors, namely, pH, adsorbate initial concentration, adsorbent dosage, and temperature were experimentally studied. To estimate the adsorption capacity of HNT, nine isotherm models were studied. Brouers-Sotolongo adsorption isotherm model was found to be the best fit. The predominant mechanism for the overall rate of for a multi-step dye adsorption process fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Mechanistic studies relate mass transfer phenomena were more likely to be dominant over diffusion process. The study of the thermodynamic parameters reveals that the process is physisorption. SEM and FTIR studies suggest the adsorption of the dye on HNT. Statistical optimization of process parameters were carried out.

The interactions between the HNT as adsorbent and DB15 dye as adsorbate showed experimental equilibrium (q_e) value of 96.00 mg g⁻¹ at pH 2 and 69.00 mg g⁻¹ at almost neutral pH. To understand the process of adsorption, nine isotherm models were studied. The adsorption follows Brouers-Sotolongo model. The interactions between HNT and DB15 are physical in nature and follows psuedo-second-order kinetics. Contact time, dye concentration, dosage and initial pH of the solution have profound influence on adsorption process. The dye-modified HNT has the potential as reinforcing material for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste. Preliminary investigations gave encouraging results.

Chapter 3 presents experimental investigations carried out using halloysite nanotubes (HNT), a relatively low-cost nanomaterial abundantly available with least toxicity for the removal of brilliant green dye from aqueous media is reported. Factors affecting adsorption

studies were carried out to assess the adsorption capacity, the kinetics and the equilibrium thermodynamics. All the experiments were designed at about pH 7. The Toth isotherm model fits best amongst nine isotherm models studied. Kinetic studies data conformed to pseudo-second-order model. Mechanistic studies suggest that the rate controlling step is predominantly dominated by intraparticle diffusion. Scanning electron microscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy were used in characterizing the adsorbent. Process optimization was carried out using Response Surface Methodology (RSM) through two-level Fractional Factorial Experimental Design (FEED) to study the influence of parameters on the process of adsorption. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to study the combined effect of the parameters. Possibilities of the use of dye-adsorbed HNT (“sludge”) for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste are suggested.

The interactions between the HNT as adsorbent and BG dye as adsorbate showed experimental equilibrium (q_e) value of 91.00 mg g⁻¹ at pH 2 and 84.00 mg g⁻¹ at almost neutral pH. To understand the process of adsorption, nine isotherm models were studied. The adsorption follows Toth isotherm model. The interactions between HNT and BG were physical in nature and follow second-order kinetics. Contact time, dye concentration, dosage and initial pH of the solution have profound influence on adsorption process. The dye-modified HNT has the potential as reinforcing material for the fabrication of the composites using plastic waste.

PART C

This part consists of two chapters and devoted to the studies on unmodified clay minerals for remediation of dyes in textile industrial effluent.

Chapter 4 explores first-ever study on the potential use of low-cost, abundantly available, eco-friendly and unmodified bentonite (Bent), montmorillonite K10 (Mt) and kaolin light (K) as adsorbents for the remediation of Direct red 13 (DR13), a bisazo dye, from textile industrial effluent (TIE) is reported. The parameters affecting the adsorption capacity, kinetics and equilibrium were evaluated. Toth isotherm model was found to be best fit for the dye uptake process. The predominant kinetic mechanism fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Film diffusion studies indicated that the external mass transfer phenomena were

more likely to be dominant over the diffusion process. The low ΔH° values indicate that the process of adsorption is physical in nature. Weak interactions like Van der Waal forces and hydrogen bonds play major roles as supported by FT-IR analysis. Statistical model was developed for optimization of adsorption processes. Prospects on the use of dye-adsorbed clay mineral for the fabrication of composites are reported.

The adsorption capacity of Bent and Mt obtained from the quadratic model developed for process optimization gave values of 801 mg g^{-1} and 436 mg g^{-1} and follows Toth's isotherm. The kinetic, mechanistic and thermodynamic studies confirm that the process is physisorption and follows second-order kinetics with a multi-step diffusion route. A broad range of pH 4 to 10 for the remediation of DR13 dye on Bent and Mt is encouraging. The high removal efficiency among studied clay minerals, followed the order Bent > Mt >>> K. The dye-adsorbed Bent and Mt minerals obtained as "sludge" can be used as filler/reinforcing materials for the fabrication of composites using plastic waste. The detailed study on the composites is in progress in our laboratory.

Chapter 5 examines the inexpensive unmodified clay minerals for the first-ever study on the potential use of low-cost, abundantly available, eco-friendly and unmodified bentonite (Bent), montmorillonite K10 (Mt) and kaolin light (K) as adsorbents for the remediation of Brilliant Green (BG), a triarylmethane dye, from textile industrial effluent (TIE) is reported. The parameters affecting the adsorption capacity, kinetics and equilibrium were evaluated. Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm model was found to be best fit for the dye uptake process. The predominant kinetic mechanism fits best to pseudo-second-order reaction. Film diffusion studies indicated that the external mass transfer phenomena were more likely to be dominant over the diffusion process. The low ΔH° values indicate that the process of adsorption is physical in nature. Weak interactions like Van der Waal forces and hydrogen bonds play major roles as supported by FT-IR analysis. Statistical model was developed for optimization of adsorption processes. Prospects on the use of dye-adsorbed clay mineral for the fabrication of composites are reported.

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PART D

This part consists of two chapters and devoted to the studies on applications of nanomaterials for remediation of dyes in textile industrial effluent.

Chapter 6 examines the Photocatalytic dye remediation of Methylene Violet by using nanomaterials like NiO/CdS nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes (CNT). The nanomaterials were mixed and made NiO/CdS-CNT nanocomposites. On comparing the efficacy of both the nanoparticles, the results were almost similar, except the CdS nanoparticles shows faster degradation rates when compared to the NiO nanoparticles.

Chapter 7 explores the use of toxic dyes such as Azobenzene for commercial applications among which solar cells were of primary interest. The Azobenzene dye can be utilized to coat on the surface of the solar cells which will increase the solar radiations absorption capacity of the solar cells. These dyes can be utilized in Dye Sensitized Solar Cells (DSSCs) which are gaining high importance in recent times. The chapter describes the use of nanomaterials TiO₂ nanoparticles and carbon nanotubes for their excellent electronic properties. TiO₂ nanoparticles acted as photocatalyst and whereas CNTs boosted conductivity and also showed the ability of their use as capacitors in the device. The solar cell efficiency was tested and found effective.

PART E

This part outlines the major conclusions and scope of the future work.